
Improving the Efficiency of using Central Bank Monetary Policy Instruments

Kholmamatov Farkhodjon Kubayevich

Tashkent State University of Economics, DSc, Professor

Abstract: Monetary policy is a critical tool used by central banks to influence a nation's economic activity, primarily by managing interest rates, controlling the money supply, and ensuring financial stability. This abstract delves into the effective use of various monetary policy instruments by central banks, highlighting the strategic deployment of these tools to achieve macroeconomic objectives such as price stability, full employment, and sustainable economic growth. Key instruments discussed include open market operations, the discount rate, and reserve requirements, each playing a distinct role in regulating the economy. The study examines the transmission mechanisms through which these instruments impact economic variables, evaluates the effectiveness of conventional versus unconventional monetary policies, and considers the challenges posed by factors such as global economic integration, technological advances, and financial market complexities. Through a comprehensive analysis, this research underscores the importance of adaptive and forward-looking monetary policies, the need for central bank independence, and the coordination with fiscal policies to enhance overall economic resilience and stability.

Key words: Interest Rates, Open Market Operations (OMO), Reserve Requirements, Quantitative Easing (QE), Forward Guidance, Inflation Targeting, Exchange Rate Policy, Credit Control, Monetary Policy Transmission Mechanism, Liquidity Management, Macro prudential Policy, Unconventional Monetary Policies, Central Bank Independence, Monetary Aggregates, Financial Market Stability, Economic Indicators.

Introduction. Monetary policy, managed by a nation's central bank, plays a crucial role in stabilizing the economy. Through the strategic use of various monetary policy instruments, central banks aim to influence economic variables such as inflation, employment, and overall economic growth. This introduction will delve into the core objectives, instruments, and the significance of monetary policy in modern economic management.

The primary objectives of monetary policy typically include:

1. **Price Stability:** Maintaining a low and stable rate of inflation is crucial to preserve the purchasing power of the currency and foster economic certainty.
2. **Full Employment:** Achieving and maintaining a high level of employment to ensure that those who want to work can find employment.
3. **Economic Growth:** Promoting sustainable economic growth through appropriate monetary interventions.
4. **Financial Market Stability:** Ensuring the stability of financial markets to prevent crises that can lead to severe economic downturns.

Central banks use monetary policy to manage economic fluctuations and achieve price stability, which means that inflation is low and stable. Central banks in many advanced economies set explicit inflation targets. Many developing countries also are moving to inflation targeting.

Analysis and results. Central banks conduct monetary policy by adjusting the supply of money, usually through buying or selling securities in the open market. Open market operations affect short-term interest rates, which in turn influence longer-term rates and economic activity. When central banks lower interest rates, monetary policy is easing. When they raise interest rates, monetary policy is tightening.

After the global financial crisis that started in 2007, central banks in advanced economies eased monetary policy by reducing interest rates until short-term rates came close to zero, limiting options for additional cuts. Some central banks used unconventional monetary policies, buying long-term bonds to further lower long-term rates. Some even took short-term rates below zero. In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, central banks took actions to ease monetary policy, provide liquidity to markets, and maintain the flow of credit. To mitigate stress in currency and bond markets, many emerging market central banks used foreign exchange interventions, and for the first time, asset purchase programs. More recently, in response to rapidly growing inflation, central banks around the world have tightened monetary policy by increasing interest rates.

Economic growth, low levels of unemployment, and a stable inflation rate are the primary goal of any country’s central bank. These goals can only be achieved if the monetary policy works effectively in the economy. Monetary authorities of any country endorse monetary policy by managing interest rate or money supply in the economy to achieve specific objectives, i.e., price stability, promoting economic growth, financial stability, and inflation control. These specific goals can only be achieved if monetary policy actions are transferred effectively in the economy. There are different transmission mechanisms through which the policy actions are transferred into the economy. This monetary transmission mechanism connects the financial system to monetary theory.

In order to achieve the goal of ensuring price stability and increase the efficiency of the interest rate channel of the transmission mechanism, the Central Bank conducts monetary policy operations.

Monetary operations are directed to the management of short-term interest rates by regulating the general liquidity of the banking system.

The Central bank carried out these operations on the basis of the interest corridor mechanism and ensure the formation of money market interest rates in a corridor of $\pm 2\%$ compared to the policy rate.

Table 1. Operational mechanism of Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan¹

Goal	Operations	Conditions	Interest rate	Task
Liquidity provision operations	REPO auctions	On 7 days (every Monday) (11:00 - 11:30)	Policy rate	Provision of temporary shortage of liquidity in the banking system
	SWAP auctions	On 7 days (every Monday) (11:30 - 12:00)		
	Overnight REPO	For 1 day (10:00 - 16:00)	Policy rate + 2%	Provision of the daily liquidity shortage in the banking system
	Overnight SWAP			
Liquidity absorbing operations	Overnight deposit operations	Overnight (10:00 - 16:00)	Policy rate - 2%	Absorbing daily excess of liquidity in the banking system
	Deposit auctions	On 7 days (every	Policy rate	Absorbing temporary excess of liquidity in the

¹ <https://cbu.uz/en/monetary-policy>

		Thursday) (11:00 - 11:30)		banking system
	Central bank's bonds	Up to 12 months (schedule based) (11:00 - 11:30)	Policy rate + 2% (upper bond)	Absorbing structural excess of liquidity in the banking system

The monetary and credit policy implemented by the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2023 was formed at a relatively strict level against the background of changes in external economic conditions, the scale of structural reforms in the national economy, and the slowdown of inflationary processes.

In particular, due to the fact that the inflation rate has moved to a downward trend and the forecasts for the end of the year also show downward dynamics, in order to curb inflationary expectations in 2022, the main rate has been reduced to 14%, and "relatively strict" monetary conditions have been maintained.

The strict conditions in the international financial markets and the devaluation of exchange rates in some trading partners, on the one hand, made it difficult to re-attract external resources to support domestic economic activity, and on the other hand, led to the widening of imbalances in currency flows.

The Central Bank will continue measures aimed at ensuring relatively tight monetary conditions in the economy until the inflation decreases to 5 percent target and the risks of its sharp increase are eliminated.

In particular, by ensuring positive real interest rates in the economy, measures will be taken aimed at the stability of the real monetary conditions index.

Higher real interest rates starting from the second half of the current year and ensuring their positive difference in the next forecast period, in turn, support saving activity and, by restraining consumer demand, provide conditions for inflation to develop on the forecast trajectory and decrease to the target in 2025.

Figure 1. Index of real monetary and credit conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Source: CBU calculations

Weakening of the real effective exchange rate (REER) in the first quarter of this year has led to some easing of relatively tight monetary conditions in the short term. According to forecasts, due to exchange rate movements and inflation of major trading partner countries, the positive REER

gap is projected to narrow in the next quarter, and from the second half of this year onward, monetary conditions are projected to shift to a tight phase

Based on the liquidity situation of the banks, the required reserve ratio for deposits in foreign currency was lowered by 4 percentage points to 14 percent in order to create conditions for reducing the interest rates on bank loans.

In 2021, the required reserve ratio on foreign currency deposits was raised to 18 percent with the aim of reducing deposit dollarization. As a result, the dollarization in deposits decreased from 40 percent at the beginning of 2021 to 30 percent as of June 1, 2024, while the dollarization in bank loans decreased from 47 percent to 42 percent.

The lowering of reserve requirements on foreign currency deposits allows banks to relieve some pressure on interest expenditures.

Moreover, based on the current liquidity situation, in order to ensure the continuity of payments, it was decided to increase the averaging ratio from 80 percent to 100 percent and return 3.0 trillion soums of funds currently available in the required reserve accounts to commercial banks.

These changes will take effect from July 1, 2024.

In the medium term, measures will be taken to further improve reserve requirements for foreign currency liabilities, including a gradual expansion of the required reserve base in 2025-2030 and a corresponding reduction in the required ratios.

Conclusion

Monetary policy is a powerful tool that central banks wield to steer the economy towards desired objectives. By understanding and effectively utilizing the various instruments at their disposal, central banks can significantly influence economic stability and growth. The intricacies of these instruments and their impact on the economy highlight the central bank's pivotal role in economic management and underscore the importance of strategic and well-informed monetary policy decisions.

Suggestions for Improvement.

1. Enhanced Communication and Transparency:

➤ Clear and consistent communication from central banks can improve the effectiveness of monetary policy. Transparency in decision-making processes helps build credibility and manage market expectations.

2. Coordination with Fiscal Policy:

➤ Monetary policy can be more effective when coordinated with fiscal policy. Joint efforts between the central bank and government can provide a more comprehensive approach to economic stabilization.

3. Macroprudential Measures:

➤ Implementing macroprudential measures, such as stress testing and capital requirements, can help ensure financial stability and reduce the risk of financial crises.

4. Innovation and Flexibility:

➤ Central banks should be open to innovative policy tools and be flexible in their approach. This includes exploring new methods such as digital currencies and incorporating financial technology in monetary policy implementation.

5. Targeted Interventions:

➤ Rather than broad-based measures, targeted interventions can be more effective in addressing specific economic issues. For instance, targeted lending programs for small businesses can have a more direct impact on economic growth.

By considering these conclusions and suggestions, central banks can enhance the effectiveness of their monetary policy instruments and better achieve their economic stability and growth objectives.

1. Alexander, William E., Tomás J.T. Baliño, and Charles Enoch, 1995, *The Adoption of Indirect Instruments of Monetary Policy*, IMF Occasional Paper No. 126 (Washington: International Monetary Fund).
2. Kuttner, Kenneth. 2004. "A Snapshot of Inflation Targeting in its Adolescence." In *The Future of Inflation Targeting*, ed. C. Kent and S. Guttman. Sydney: Reserve Bank of Australia, 6-47.
3. Jansen, David-Jan, and Jakob De Haan. 2007. "Were Verbal Efforts to Support The Euro Effective? A High-frequency Analysis of ECB Statements." *European Journal of Political Economy*, 23(1): 245-259.
4. Issing, Otmar. 2005. "Communication, Transparency, Accountability – Monetary Policy in the Twenty-First Century." *Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis Review*, 87(2): 65-83.
5. Heinemann, Friedrich, and Karin Ullrich. 2007. "Does it Pay to Watch Central Bankers Lips? The Information Content of ECB Wording." *Swiss Journal of Economics and Statistics* 3: 155-85.
6. Fratzscher, Marcel. 2006. "On the Long-Term Effectiveness of Exchange Rate Communication and Interventions." *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 25(1): 146-67.
7. Ehrmann, Michael, and Marcel Fratzscher. 2007c. "The Timing of Central Bank Communication." *European Journal of Political Economy*, 23(1): 124-45.
8. Berardi, Michele, and John Duffy. 2007. "The Value of Central Bank Transparency When Agents Are Learning." *European Journal of Political Economy*, 23(1): 9-29.
9. Ivo.J.M. Arnold, Beau Soederhuizen "Bank stability and refinancing operations during the crisis: which way causality?" *Research in International Business and Finance* 43 (2018) p.80
10. "Global macro-financial shocks and expected default frequencies in the euro area" by O. Castrén, S. Déés and F. Zaher, February 2008.
11. Moiseev S.R. *Monetary policy: theory and practice*. – M.: "Moscow Financial and Industrial Academy", 2011. - 221 p.
12. Soto H.U. *Money, bank credit and economic cycles*. Translation from English – M.: "Socium", 2008. – 663 p.
13. Azizov U.O. *Effect of monetary and credit and fiscal levers in ensuring stable growth of the economy of Uzbekistan*. Monograph. - T.: "Economy-Finance", 2013. p. 35.
14. <http://www.cbu.uz>. (Website of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan).